

COOKING BEHAVIOR AND CREATIVITY: IMPLICATIONS ON JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' CULINARY PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Cooking is a vital life skill that promotes good eating habits and provides individuals with the knowledge and skills to prepare nutritious meals for their overall well-being. This study examines the influence of cooking practices on culinary proficiency among Grade 9 and 10 students in a private school located in Malaybalay City, Bukidnon. The study explored various elements like the choice of ingredients, meal preparation procedures, trash disposal methods, hygiene standards, time management, and culinary innovation. The research design utilizes a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach, both quantitative and qualitative elements. The findings showed that students have favorable cooking habits, including item selection, meal preparation routines, waste management, cleanliness practices, and time management. However, poor culinary performance is influenced by time management, attention to detail, accurate methods, and cooking focus. The study found that students have a strong foundation in culinary skills, with most performing at "High" levels. However, they did not show a significant influence of their cooking behavior or creativity on their performance. The participants' comments revealed two themes: personal factors and mismatch between ideas and execution, which despite their innovative menu ideas, posed challenges in presenting their meals. The study suggests that the Future Researchers should investigate additional characteristics and themes that could impact students' culinary performance and conduct their study in a public-school setting.

Keywords: *cooking behavior, creativity, culinary performance*

INTRODUCTION

Cooking is a life skill that significantly impacts personal health and culinary expertise. It is more than a mere routine; it is an art that shapes how individuals select, prepare, and consume food, directly affecting their nutrition and wellness (Van Kesteren & Evans, 2020; Mosko & Delach, 2021; Marcus, 2013). Mastering these skills is crucial for tenth-grade students, as it instills a sense of culinary creativity and proficiency, equipping them with the ability to make informed dietary choices. This period of skill acquisition is crucial as it lays the foundation for a lifetime of healthy eating habits and a robust understanding of nutritional science. By integrating practical cooking experience with theoretical knowledge about food and health, these students are empowered to lead healthier, more balanced lives.

Cultural education programs have a profound impact on dietary habits and the potential to cultivate a new generation of skilled and confident home chefs. Recent studies in the Philippines emphasize the critical role of involving the youth in cooking and food preparation. The Department of Education's Cookery program aims to teach healthy cooking skills to students from a young age, with 87% of students actively cooking or preparing their meals.

Research underlines the significant impact of culinary education on dietary behaviors and cooking confidence. A 2015 study by Utter et al. showed that culinary education leads to positive changes in dietary behavior and enhanced cooking confidence and knowledge. Research by Reicks et al., (2014) found that cooking programs contribute to favorable dietary changes and improved cooking abilities.

The proposed study on the cooking behavior of Grade 10 students and its influence on their culinary performance is particularly significant. It will contribute to filling the research gap by exploring how culinary education influences students' long-term culinary skills and behavior and provide a deeper understanding of how these shape students' engagement and proficiency in cooking. By examining the specific behaviors and performance outcomes of junior high school students in culinary activities, the study will offer valuable insights into how early culinary education can mold future cooking habits and preferences. This research can be instrumental in shaping educational strategies and policies to enhance the effectiveness of culinary education, ensuring it meets the diverse needs of students and equips them with the skills necessary for lifelong healthy eating habits and culinary proficiency.

Research Objectives

The study investigates the influence of cooking behavior on the culinary performance of Grade 9 and 10 students in a private school in Malaybalay City Bukidnon. It aims to understand their selection of ingredients, meal preparation routines, waste management, hygiene practices, time management, culinary creativity, performance, and whether these factors significantly influence their culinary skills.

Methodology

This research aims to analyze the cooking behavior and creative culinary expression of junior high school students, specifically Grades 9 and 10, ages 14 to 16, using a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach. The study used a total population sampling technique, involving all Grade 9 and 10 students enrolled in the Home Economics program or TLE Subject at a private, nonsectarian junior high school in Bukidnon, Philippines for the academic year 2023-2024. The questionnaire used is bidirectional, consisting of two distinct phases: gathering detailed information about participants' cooking behaviors and evaluating their culinary performance. The 12 students representing the different section in grade 9 and 10 are the participants for interview. The research instrument will be crafted from relevant studies, such as Horng et al.'s(2009) work on the impact of creative culinary curriculum on the creative culinary process and performance. Subject-matter experts will be sought to ensure content validity, and a pilot test will be conducted on 40 Grade 9 students to evaluate the questionnaire's effectiveness. The data analysis involved different statistical tools for different problems, ensuring a comprehensive and methodical analysis of the collected data.

Framework

The research hypothesizes that the cooking behavior of Grade 9 and 10 participants will significantly influence their culinary performance. This hypothesis is supported by Constructivist Learning Theory, which emphasizes the social aspects of learning and the importance of collaborative and interactive cooking activities. David Kolb's Experiential Learning Model further underpins this hypothesis, stating that learning involves a continuous cycle of experiencing, reflecting, conceptualizing, and experimenting.

In culinary education, students actively engage in cooking, not just performing tasks but also participating in a dynamic learning process. This experiential, hands-on nature, coupled with social interaction and guided learning, significantly enhances the culinary performance of Junior high school students. The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) suggests that students learn most effectively when performing tasks slightly beyond their current level of competence, but within their capacity to achieve with guidance.

The study focuses on examining the variable of Cooking Behavior and culinary creativity among Junior High school student-participants and culinary performance. Key components of this behavior include Meal Preparation Routines, Ingredient Selection, Waste Management, Hygiene Practices, Time Management, and Culinary Creativity. Each of these elements plays a vital role in shaping the overall cooking behavior of the students and will be evaluated to gain a deeper understanding of their culinary skills and practices.

Food waste management behaviors among students are another crucial aspect to consider. Studies in Malaysia have shown the impact of socio-demographic

characteristics such as education, employment, and income on food waste creation. Additionally, research on food waste behavior and awareness in Malaysia has revealed the need for effective waste management systems to raise awareness and solve the food waste problem among young consumers. These findings provide valuable insights into the relationship between waste management and cooking behavior.

Culinary creativity is a crucial aspect of culinary performance, involving the ability to create unique and culturally rich culinary creations. This creative culinary process involves exploring and experimenting with diverse ingredients and techniques while presenting dishes in an aesthetically pleasing manner. It is influenced by factors such as individual tastes and preferences, cultural and societal influences, and the accessibility of cooking resources.

Culinary performance refers to the ability of an individual to prepare, cook, and present food in a professional and aesthetically pleasing manner. Factors that can affect culinary creativity include training and education, experience, and access to quality ingredients and equipment. In the context of home cooking, culinary creativity is influenced by several key factors, each playing a significant role in shaping the overall cooking experience.

Mise-en place is a culinary concept that ensures that everything required is readily available and all necessary preparation has been completed on time. This concept extends beyond the physical actions of putting things in place and guarantees a well-regulated workplace, representing a higher cognitive activity of thinking in a specific manner.

In sum, culinary creativity is a multifaceted aspect of culinary performance that is influenced by various factors such as hygiene practices, time management, and cultural activities. By mastering these aspects, individuals can enhance their culinary skills and contribute to better dietary choices and overall health.

Mastery of Food and Taste is a crucial skill for culinary professionals and students, encompassing a deep understanding of flavors, cooking techniques, ingredients, nutrition, cultural understanding, sensory evaluation, creativity, and innovation.

Food Presentation Skills are also essential in culinary education, extending beyond mere food arrangement to visual appeal. High school students are taught that the aesthetics of food presentation are as essential as its taste, reinforced by multimedia web-based technologies. This training involves not only creativity and artistry in using colors, textures, and garnishes but also the development of technical skills, including proficient knife techniques, plating methods, and culinary tool usage.

Mastery in presentation skills enables students to communicate their culinary ideas effectively, conveying themes, traditions, or personal styles through their creations. This approach cultivates meticulous attention to detail and fosters a mindset aimed at achieving excellence.

In educational settings, presenting food facilitates engagement and offers opportunities for peer and instructor feedback, enriching the learning experience. The culinary performance of adolescent learners is shaped by a combination of skill development, culinary knowledge, and artistry, integrating practical cooking techniques with academic learning and emphasizing creativity, teamwork, and communication. This holistic approach enhances their ability to create nutritious and flavorful dishes, improve diet quality, and develop proficiency in food presentation, merging the art of culinary creativity with the science of nutrition for a comprehensive culinary education.

In conclusion, the cooking behavior of adolescent learners is a multifaceted concept, influenced by personal and socio-demographic factors, and intricately linked to various components of culinary education such as meal preparation, ingredient selection, and culinary creativity. The interplay between cooking behavior and their possible influence on culinary performance is visually represented in a graphical form.

Figure 1. The schematic presentation of the study showing the interplay of the variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem 1. How often do the participants demonstrate the following cooking behaviors?

- 1.1 Ingredient Selection;
- 1.2 Meal Preparation Routines;
- 1.3 Waste Management;
- 1.4 Hygiene Practices; and,
- 1.5 Time Management?

Table 1.
Summary Table of Cooking Behavior of Grade 9 and 10 Students

Dimensions of Cooking Behavior of Grade 9 and 10 Students	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Ingredient Selection	4.27	Always	0.46
Meal Preparation Routines	4.09	Most of the time	0.53
Waste Management	4.12	Sometimes	0.54
Hygiene Practices	4.65	Rarely	0.39
Time Management	4.00	Never	0.68
Overall Cooking Behavior of Grade 10 Students	4.23	Most of the time	0.43

Table 1 shows that students in grade 9 and 10 demonstrate high to extremely high levels of cooking behavior in all areas evaluated. The category with the highest mean score, "Always," for hygiene practices, highlights how important it is to uphold standards of cleanliness and hygiene when preparing meals. Meal preparation procedures, ingredient selection, and waste management all get high mean scores and are classified as "Most of the time," demonstrating competence in these areas. Although time management is still ranked as "most of the time," it has a mean score that is marginally lower than other dimensions, indicating that there is still opportunity for development when it comes to efficiently managing time when cooking.

Problem 2. What is the participants' extent of culinary creativity?

Table 2.
Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Participants' Extent of Culinary Creativity

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	26	32.50
3.51-4.50	High	44	55.00
2.51-3.50	Moderate	9	11.25
1.51-2.50	Low	1	1.25

1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		80	100.0
Overall Mean		4.20	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.59	

Table 2 shows the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of participants' culinary creativity. The average score of 4.20 indicates high culinary originality, with 32.50% falling into the "Very High" and 55.00% in the "High" categories. The majority have moderate to high levels of inventiveness, with 1.25% falling into the "Low" group. There are some differences in creativity within the group, with moderate variability in responses. Studies show that regular use of convenience cooking products and a willingness to try new things are linked to greater cooking innovation. The high mean score of 4.49 indicates a strong positive attitude towards culinary experimentation. The other indicators, such as being open to exploring innovative cooking ideas and believing culinary creativity enhances the overall dining experience, also show high mean scores, indicating a strong positive attitude towards culinary creativity among participants. Participants' openness to innovative ideas, joy in expressing creativity through cooking, and belief in the improvement of dining experiences through culinary creativity collectively contribute to a culture of experimentation, innovation, and enjoyment in the culinary field.

Problem 3. What is the level of the participants' culinary performance?

Table 3.
Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Students' Culinary Performance

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	4	5.0
3.51-4.50	High	61	76.25
2.51-3.50	Moderate	15	18.75
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.0
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.0
Total		80	100.0
Overall Mean		3.99	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.45	

Table 3 displays the culinary performance of students in a culinary education program. The majority of students (76.25%) are classified as "High" performers, indicating high culinary proficiency. However, 18.75% fit into the "Moderate" group, indicating a moderate degree of culinary proficiency. Most participants show at least a moderate level of culinary skill, with no low or very low scores. The standard deviation of 0.45 suggests little variability in responses.

The effectiveness of culinary students in foodservice laboratories is determined by their ability to achieve industry goals and outcomes. A critical area of expertise for

students studying culinary nutrition is cooking methods and procedures. Nonacademic assessment methods, such as performance measurement devices, are used to assess student performance in culinary education.

Problem 4. Do the participants' cooking behavior and their creativity significantly influence their culinary performance?

Ho₁. The participants' cooking behavior and their creativity do not significantly influence their culinary performance.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of the Possible Influence of the Participants' Cooking Behavior and their Creativity on their Culinary Performance

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	3.78	.520		7.27	.000
Cooking Behavior	-.205	.222	-.192	-.924	.358
Culinary Creativity	.258	.159	.337	1.62	.110
Model Summary					
R = .203	R ² = .041	Adjusted R ² = .016	F = 1.65	p = .199	

The result of the study in Table 4 reveals that factors such as cooking experience, culinary training, access to resources, and individual taste preferences do not significantly influence culinary performance. Other elements like technical proficiency, culinary method knowledge, adaptability to various cuisines, and interpersonal skills also impact culinary performance. Formal culinary education and prior food industry experience can enhance confidence and knowledge, while experience with diverse culinary styles and creative flavors expands horizons. However, the complexity of culinary performance may vary due to personality, motivation, and learning approaches.

An interview was conducted to validate the study's results on why culinary behavior and creativity do not influence the performance thus, two themes emerged based on the responses given by the participants, which highlight their experiences and difficulties in presenting their meals, despite having creative menu ideas and good culinary behavior. These themes provide valuable insights into the challenges faced by the participants and the factors that may have contributed to the lack of significant influence of cooking behavior and creativity on culinary performance. By exploring these themes further, the researcher can gain a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between various

factors that shape culinary performance and identify potential areas for intervention and support to help students enhance their culinary skills and achieve better outcomes.

The following are the two themes that came out from the study gathered namely: Personal Factor and Mismatch of Culinary Ideas and Execution.

Personal Factor

There were three categories under personal factor namely: time restrictions, lack of focus, lack of attention to detail, and environmental factors. The research study on personal factors influencing the culinary performance of students from the study of Harrel (2021), "How Background Factors Affect Culinary Skills and Knowledge," this study investigates the impact of a student's prior experience in cooking, grocery shopping, and other relevant background elements on their culinary expertise and knowledge. This study explores how individual characteristics, such as innate attributes including genetic predispositions, life experiences, cognitive abilities, and personality traits, might influence attitudes, actions, emotions, and thoughts, ultimately impacting culinary performance.

Mismatch of Culinary Ideas and Execution

There were three categories which are; inadequate execution of cooking techniques and cooking skills, and overestimation of skills. The culinary sector is frequently perceived as a domain where creativity, innovation, and artistry intersect. Chefs and culinary specialists aim to conceive and create distinctive and captivating foods that stimulate the senses. Nevertheless, the process of transforming these culinary concepts into practical implementation can be quite demanding. An essential concern is in the inherent objectivity involved in the perception of taste and palatability. According to the study of Gunay, (2023). A recipe for culinary creativity: Defining characteristics of creative chefs and their process, explores the elements contributing to culinary innovation and the obstacles chefs encounter when translating their concepts into actual execution. The difference between the chef's conceptualization and the customer's interpretation can lead to annoyance and affect the overall gastronomic proficiency of trainees. By addressing these challenges through a multifaceted approach, culinary students can better translate their creative ideas into visually appealing and well-executed dishes.

Conclusions

The study provides valuable insights into the cooking behavior, culinary creativity, and performance of Grade 9 and 10 students. While the findings indicate that students demonstrate competence in various areas of cooking behavior and exhibit a strong foundation of culinary skills, there are opportunities for improvement and growth. Although the regression analysis did not find a significant influence of cooking behavior and creativity on culinary performance, the qualitative analysis revealed several themes that shed light on the challenges students face when attempting to showcase their culinary skills. Thus, the results of the study affirm the Constructivist Learning theory where it stated that learning is an active, socially interactive process in which knowledge is constructed through experiences and interactions with the environment and others (Vygotsky, 1978) as cited by Kurt,S.(2021) in his article on constructivist learning theory.

Further, Vygotsky's emphasis on the social aspects of learning aligns with the idea that culinary skills can be significantly developed through collaborative and interactive cooking activities to which it was shown in the themes that emerged.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations have been suggested:

1. TLE Teachers: that they emphasize the value of culinary education and training for students to improve their technical proficiency, culinary method knowledge, adaptability to other cuisines, and interpersonal skills, all of which can have a substantial impact on their culinary performance and consider providing individualized training or small group sessions to address students' specific requirements and obstacles, such as mastering new cooking techniques or ingredients.
2. School Administrators: that curriculum development may be enhanced through incorporating time management, attention to detail, correct methodology, and focus into the culinary curriculum to prepare students for the challenges and demands of the culinary business.
3. Laboratory In-charge: ensure that students have access to the resources they need to develop and perform well in the kitchen, such as quality food, cooking equipment, and instructional materials.
4. Future Researchers: that they will look into the other factors and themes that may affect the culinary performance of the students and conduct their study in a public school.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research processed commenced with obtaining approval from the Lourdes College Research and Ethics Committee (LCREC), ensuring that ethical considerations were met before the conduct of the study. To ethically engage Grade 9 and 10 students, who are minors, the researchers secured informed consent from their parents or guardians and informed assent from the students themselves. The participants were given a clear, age-appropriate explanation of the study to gain their assent, ensuring they comprehend their participation's nature and significance. The participants were provided with comprehensive information about the study's goals and importance, enabling them to make an informed decision about whether or not to voluntarily participate. This dual approach respects both the legal guardians' authority and the minors' autonomy. The participant's autonomy is respected and acknowledged by the researchers, to reimburse the participants time and effort in participating in the conduct of the study, a simple snack was given and a token was also given to the inter-rater. All data collected for the study were handled with the highest confidentiality and secrecy, in accordance with the Data Privacy Act.

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